

SOME PROBLEMATIC ISSUES IN TRANSLATION OF ANIMAL IDIOMS INTO DIFFERENT LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses common problems in translation of animal idioms into different languages and analyses some strategies that can play significant role in translation. The subject of this study is the animal idioms and their translation methods. The aim of this article is to identify the most flexible ways of translation and using the different theories in translating the English idioms into different languages.

Idioms are interesting, colorful and fascinating aspect of the language. Idioms with their frequent appearance are commonly recognized as the core and essence of language and culture. Without idioms, any language is sure to be proved lifeless. The prominent translation theorist Eugene A. Nida (2001) maintained that idioms usually carry more impact than non-idiomatic expressions because of their close identification with a particular language and culture. Idioms hold great interest of linguists. As the saying puts it, "A thousand-li starts with the first step". Some basic knowledge is needed to further idiomatic studies.

As Nida (1964) pointed that the purpose and characteristics of translation are to exchange idea and culture. Translation promotes understanding among different cultures. In translation, the principle of "seeking the common ground while reserving differences" should be practiced.

In the process of translating the animal idioms, we can adopt three translation strategies which are described below:

Literal Translation

Literal translation refers to strictly following the writing style and manner of the original. It is the rendering of text from one language to another. It aims at maintaining the image, national and local features, and language style of the source language. Some of the animal idioms in English, Russian, Indonesian, and Uzbek have similarities in terms of meaning, language style, and the most important culture. In the process of translating animal idioms, if the equivalent idiom can be found in the source language and the target language, we can translate it directly, not altering the original sentence pattern, structure, image, and figure of speech so as to arise the equivalence of response of the readers. Take the following idioms as examples: *As cunning as a fox* in Russian

хитрый как лиса, in Uzbek *tulkidekayyor*. The adverb "as...as..." is used when we are comparing two things or two situations. In Russian, *как* means (подчинительный союз в конструкциях сравнения: словно, будто) subordinate conjunction in comparison constructs: *as if*, *as if*. In Uzbek, it means suffix *-dekor -day*. This translation is structural equivalent. A fox is defined as a person who is clever and able to get what he wants by influencing or tricking other people in the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (1995). While in Uzbek also has the same image. According to the same experience of people from two different cultures, the word "fox" is endowed with the image of "cunning." As a result, this translation is cultural equivalent. This phenomenon is called cultural overlap. Basing on the common cognitive experience, people with different cultures show the same attitude towards the same animal. In such a case, people can understand the translation thoroughly, and the animal image of the source language can be conveyed and understood when we translate it literally.

Image-Shift Translation

As what mentioned above, language is closely related to culture. We cannot analyze the language from a deep angle and translate it faithfully, expressively, and elegantly without strict attention to the culture. Because of the influence of different cultures, which contain differences in lifestyle caused by different geographical features, differences in custom and various allusions, people have their own habits to express the same content. Under the circumstances, we can replace the images of source language with

the proper images of target language. We call it "image-shift translation." The method of shifting the image is widely used. For example, *puppy love* is equal to *cintamonyet* in Indonesian or *when pigs fly* is equal to *Когда рак на горе свистнет* (literally "when a crayfish whistles on top of a hill") in Russian, *tuyaningdumiyergatekkanda* (literally "when the camel's tail touches the ground") in Uzbek. The puppy plays the role of monkey in Indonesian and the pig plays the role of crayfish in Russian and camel in Uzbek. We call it "cultural clash" when two cultures are not equivalent to each other. The cultural clash may lead to misunderstanding on the source language. Therefore, when we translate the source language into the target language, we should pay more attention to the cultural background knowledge.

Free Translation

Free translation means translating the content without paying much attention to language style and rhetorical devices applied to the source language. It aims at conveying the meaning, not following the original words exactly. Due to the difference in language structure and cultural background, neither literal translation nor image-shifted translation can convey the cultural connotation from the source language to target language correctly. On this condition, we should apply to free translation, such as *skill two birds with one stone* or in Russian *убить двух зайцев одним выстрелом*. The meaning is *to solve two problems at one time with a single action*. In Indonesia, it is *sekali mending dua tiga pulau terlampaui*. We cannot translate this idiom word-for-word,

like *membunuh dua burung dengan satu batu* nor replace the animal word with another one from the target language. Although the free translation cannot follow the original words exactly, it can convey the original meaning precisely.

To conclude, it can be said that the translations were categorized on the basis of the method by which they were

translated as idioms with similar meaning and similar form, idioms with similar meaning but different form, paraphrases or idioms with more possible translations and other different strategies. Each idiom can be translated from source language into target language by different strategies, not necessarily a specific one. It is better to take most suitable ways for translation, to give exact and proper meaning.

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